

Competitive Advantage in the Expressive Content of Advertising Messages Broadcast in Kinshasa the Case of Savon Mateja

Musoni M'pele Jacques
University of Kinshasa

Abstract:- Competitive advantage is a resource that a product possesses, making it competitive in the marketplace. The consumer buys not only the product, but also the promise it offers. The promise, in turn, contains the competitive advantage that contributes to customer satisfaction. Before making a purchase, consumers look for information about the product that can solve their problems. Whether users or consumers are influenced by Mateja soap advertising, given the competitive environment on the market. In a competitive environment, companies are obliged to implement various marketing strategies to ensure the market positioning of their product. Competitive advantage is considered to be the reason for a product's existence, as it provides information on the benefits that the product can bring to consumers.

I. INTRODUCTION

In a context of remarkable competitiveness, companies resort to competitive advantage to set themselves apart from the competition. It should be noted that the consumer buys a product on the basis of the attributes, characteristics and promise offered by that product. To sell, brands must inform, inspire confidence, arouse enthusiasm, seduce and convince. This can be achieved with a sound understanding of the mechanisms of communication¹.

Advertising discourse is both conative and denotative on the one hand, while the message is manifest, informative and descriptive on the other. It is more latent, insinuating implicit codes that are not consciously identifiable. Over time, advertising messages have become more sophisticated, moving from a desire to inform to a desire to seduce consumers by associating them with the brand's universe.²

This quest for satisfaction is the basis of consumer motivation. This is what we need to see in the various advertising messages from advertisers. It's not enough to simply pass on a message containing the benefits sought by consumers, but it would be better to communicate them well by putting forward evidence or testimonials that could subsequently convince or persuade the receiver. Knowing and understanding your targets is one of the keys to

successful advertising. It's all about uncovering consumers' deepest motivations, including those they haven't yet clearly expressed. Needs, expectations and perceptions must also be studied in order to better understand how consumers obtain information and make choices.³

In this way, the information sought corresponds to the competitive advantage that satisfies the psychological needs of consumers. Competitive advantage represents the substantial potential of a product. This resource must be effectively defended in order to arouse public interest in a product.⁴

The role of a product is to satisfy a need, and this is achieved through the competitive advantage that ensures a gain for the customer. In doing so, the competitive advantage must be unique and rare in order to persuade the public. This resource available to a product must promote the good it presents through its compositions.

Competitive advantage contributes to product preference and has the capacity to attract potential, current and non-relative customers to a company. To position itself on the market, a product must promote a unique competitive advantage that identifies it and differentiates it from the competition.

It's important to design powerful messages capable of influencing consumer behavior, with arguments that highlight the product's competitive advantages. Hence the questions we ask:

- What are the tangible, visible components of Mateja soap's competitive advantage?
- How do the components of Mateja soap's competitive advantage communicate?
- How does the Kinshasa public perceive these competitive advantages?

The competitive advantages promoted by Marsavco consist in the treatment and elimination of scabies, acne, psoriasis and personal hygiene. Apart from the Monganga

³BARRE,S. et GAYRARD-CARRERA,A.-MARIE, *Op. Cit*, p. 70

⁴NKONSONLOMBI, Toh, Notes de cours de la communication globale (interne et externe),L2 CO, UPN,2019,p.16.

¹ BARRE,S. et GAYRARD-CARRERA,A.-MARIE, *La boîte à outils de la publicité*, Paris, éd. DUNOD,2015,p.52.

² Idem

soap that the company sells to the market, this is even its competitive advantage, which in turn benefits many consumers and attracts public attention. In addition to media advertising, La Marsavco has used point-of-sale advertising for 'Mateja' soap, which has convinced many consumers. The Kinshasa public perceives the competitive advantages of Mateja soap as an effective product.

In order to place this research, we will the theory demand launched by LANCASTER, K.J. It constitutes an announcement and its development will take place in the first chapter. We will attempt to demonstrate how this theory will be used in our work.

➤ *We Shall use the following Methods:*

- Quantitative research: this is a method that seeks to measure consumer behavior. They are used to quantify consumer attitudes using a survey questionnaire.

➤ *Definition of key Concepts*

After exploring the theory we will use throughout our work. We will study the concepts that are important for understanding the material.

➤ *Communication*

The notion of communication is polysemous. Every human being's primary need is to communicate. Living beings communicate from birth, since breathing is already a form of communication.

According to Patrick CHARAUDEAU, communication is the action of acting on others. Human beings conceive messages with the aim of modifying or influencing the behavior of their interlocutors. Communication can also be defined as a closed circuit between transmission and reception, establishing a symmetrical relationship between the activity of the sender, whose sole role is to decode these same messages, and that of the receiver. As far as Daniel CHARRON is concerned, communication is the transmission of data, information, ideas, knowledge or know-how by a sender through a channel with a view to influencing the receiver.⁵

In this respect, communication is understood as a process of manipulation, change, modification or transformation. Here, communication is based on the principles of influence, as every speaking subject.

In short, communication is the action of communicating something to someone, a set of information communicated in this way, or the technical means by which people exchange information using a code, a language and a communication channel that can be written, oral or audiovisual.⁶

⁵CHARROND, *An introduction to communication*, Montréal, éd. PUQ, , 1999, p7

⁶ DECAUDIN J.M, *Marketing communication*, Paris , 3è éd. Economica, , 2004, p.6

➤ *Sales Promotion*⁷

Sales promotion is defined as all actions aimed at influencing consumer behavior (current and potential) by means of an immediate material incentive.

Sales promotion refers to all marketing activities that provide a value or an incentive and whose role is to stimulate sales in the very short term to the sales team, distributors or final consumers.

➤ *Media Advertising*⁸

Media Advertising is a form of communication disseminated by companies or organizations after the purchase of space in major media such as the press, television, radio, cinema, billboards and the Internet. This form of communication is widely used by companies for their products and services, and is more familiar to consumers. Above all, media advertising is a technique at the service of marketing communications strategy.

➤ *Point-of-sale Advertising (POS)*

Point-of-sale advertising is a technique for communicating directly to the consumer at the point of sale, using posters, shelf dressing, coupon or leaflet dispensers, sound messages and interactive information terminals.

According to DECAUDIN , point-of-sale advertising is the set of means used by an advertiser to optimize the presentation of its products at the point of sale. This technique has a real capacity to create and develop brand awareness. It enables us to reach consumers at the point of purchase, just before they make a purchase. It can trigger an act of purchase by a consumer frequenting the point of sale, including impulse purchases.

II. THE PERCEPTION OF THE COMMUNICATIVE ELEMENTS OF MATEJA SOAP ADVERTISING BY RESIDENTS OF THE INTERCHANGE DISTRICT

This third chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of the results of the survey carried out among residents of the Lemba district of Echangeur. The results of this survey are intended to capture the perception of the competitive advantage of "Mateja" soap as expressed by the content of advertising. The views and opinions of the respondents will be used in the analysis of this survey.

We have focused on the quantitative method. Advertising is a communication technique designed to motivate consumers' purchasing behavior by highlighting the competitive advantages of a product.

⁷ BELCH E &alii, *Marketing communication, an integrated perspective*, Montréal, éd. ChanelièreInc, , 2005, p9.

⁸ DECAUDIN Jean Marc, *opacity*, p113.

A. In Addition to our Method, we use the Following Techniques:

- Sample survey technique: translation of respondents' reactions into frequencies and percentages, in order to present and analyze the results.
- This chapter is divided into two sections:
- The first section describes the procedures involved in any scientific survey,
- The second section analyses and interprets the survey results. The formula for calculating percentages is as follows:
- $\% = \frac{F}{N} * 100$
- $\% =$ Percentage
- F= Frequency or number of observations in a category
- N= Sample size (n=100).

B. Scientific Investigation Procedures

C. Population

The study population is made up of different people from various categories found in the field, whom we are going to survey. Our study population consists of residents of the Echangeur district.

D. Sample

A sample is understood as a small quantity of individuals or subjects, detached from a whole, which allows us to form an exact idea of the whole, to apprehend its quality or to draw a conclusion about this organic whole.

Our study sample is essentially made up of 50 subjects, all residents of Lemba, in the Echangeur district. This is a random sample of our study population. The subjects in this sample were selected on the basis of acceptability and availability. To this end, only those people who agreed to help us collect information about the survey were selected.

E. Surveys and their Duration (purpose, Questionnaire and Methods of Administration)

Information on the motivations, understandings, opinions and attitudes of a specific audience is rarely, if

ever, found in existing and available literature. That's why we resort to the survey technique, which is an excellent way of quantifying the opinions or reactions of a given population.

It is a truthful source that lays the foundations for the expectations, motivations and reactions of a target audience. Scientific studies are concerned with the social facts observable in the community, which arise from the behaviours and attitudes adopted by people. It is very useful to know the true opinion built up by human beings through a sample survey. Theoretical facts can be collected from the library, but this is not the case for realities embodied in people.

For this purpose, we devised a survey questionnaire on the perception of Mateja soap's competitive advantage, based on the content of the advertisement sent to a specialized audience of intellectuals. This population, living in the commune of Lemba, will provide us with information derived from an objective judgment, manifest or latent, on the performance of Mateja soap.

Our survey took one week to complete. It was aimed at a population essentially made up of Lemba residents. The interest of such a selection lies in the technical and complex nature of our subject of study.

We opted for direct administration of our survey questionnaire, with subjects filling in their questionnaires and handing them in directly on site. In the event of any misunderstanding or grey area, we make a point of clarifying our respondents. Let us say that we were sympathetic to all our respondents, and that a spirit of open communication and listening characterized this survey.

F. Analysis and Interpretation of Respondents' Reactions

G. Analysis of Respondents' Reactions

- *Closed and Open Questions*

Table 1 Age Variable

AGE	Fréquency	Pourcentage
18-22 ans	30	60
23-27 ans	15	30
28-32 ans	3	6
36 et plus	2	4
Sum	50	100

This table shows that of the 100 people in our sample, 30 subjects (60%) are aged between 18 and 22, 15 subjects (30%) are aged between 23 and 27, 3 subjects (6%) are aged between 28 and 32, and 2 subjects (4%) are aged between 36 and over.

Table 2 Occupational Variable

Occupation	Fréquency	Pourcentage
Teacher	10	20
Students	30	60
Shopkeepers	10	20
Sum	50	100

This table shows that 60 subjects or 60% are students, 10 respondents or 10% are shopkeepers and finally 10 subjects or 10% are teachers.

➤ *Thematic Questions*

Table 3 Do you know Mateja Soap?

Reactions	Fréquency	Pourcentage
Yes	50	100
No	-	0
Sum	50	100

The table shows that 100% of the 50 people surveyed were familiar with Mateja soap.

Table 4 How did you Find out About this Soap?

Reactions	Fréquency	Pourcentage
Télévision	40	80
Outdoor	7	14
Radio	1	2
Word of mouth	2	4
Press	-	-
Sum	50	100

From this table, it can be seen that among the means by which Mateja soap became known, 40 subjects or 80% of those surveyed knew about it through television, 7 subjects or 14% said it was through posters, 2 subjects or 4% said it was through word of mouth, and finally 2 subjects or 4% knew about it through radio.

Table 5 In which Soap Category Would you Classify Mateja Soap?

Reactions	Fréquency	Pourcentage
Toilet soap	1	2
Antibacterial soap	3	6
Dermatological soap	45	90
Household soap	-	-
Other soaps to be specified	1	2
Sum	50	100

Out of a total of 50 respondents, the table shows that 45 subjects (90%) say that Mateja soap represents dermatological soap for them; 3 respondents (6%) represent toilet soap and finally 1 respondent (2%) has opted for others to be specified.

Table 6 How do you rate mateja's advertising?

Réactions	Fréquency	Pourcentage
Understanding after exposure	20	40
Good, but understanding of message after several exposures	15	30
Not legible on the market	5	10
Legible and visible on the market	7	14
More or less suitable	3	6
Sum	50	100

This table shows that, out of the total number of people surveyed, 20 subjects (40%) found the ad comprehensible after one exposure, 15 subjects (30%) good, but the message comprehensible after several exposures; 5 subjects (10%) thought the ad was legible and visible on the market, 7 subjects (14%) thought it was more or less adaptable, and finally 3 subjects (6%) said it was not legible on the market.

Table 7 Do you use Mateja Soap?

Feedback	Fréquency	Pourcentage
Yes	45	90
No	5	10
Sum	50	100

As far as Mateja soap consumers and users are concerned, the table shows that 45 subjects (90%) buy and use the product, while 5 respondents (10%) are neither consumers nor users.

Table 8: How do you Benefit From this Soap?

Réactions	Fréquency	Pourcentage
Ensures personal hygiene	8	16
Moisturizes and purifies skin	5	10
Invigorates and beautifies the skin	10	20
Protects against skin diseases	25	50
Treats skin diseases caused by accidents with lightening products	2	4
Sum	50	100

The table shows that, out of a total of 60 subjects who identified a benefit that encouraged them to buy Mateja soap, 25 subjects (50%) said that it protected against skin diseases; 10 subjects (20%) said that Mateja soap ensured personal hygiene; 8 subjects (16%) said that Mateja soap invigorated the skin and made it more beautiful; 5 subjects (10%) said that it treated the skin from diseases caused by accidents involving lightening products; 5 subjects (2%) said that Mateja soap moisturized and purified the skin.

Table 9: Do you Regularly buy Mateja Soap?

Réactions	Fréquency	Pourcentage
A few times	28	54
Several times	8	16
Quite often	10	20
Regularly	4	8
Sum	50	100

The table below shows that 28 subjects (54%) buy Mateja soap a few times, 10 subjects (20%) buy it regularly, 8 subjects (16%) buy Mateja soap fairly often, and 4 subjects (8%) buy Mateja soap several times.

➤ *Open Questions*

- Why do you prefer to use mateja soap? :
- The price of this soap shows its quality on the market,
- This soap is effective and improves infected skin.
- It purifies the skin against mucous membranes
- It is totally composed of natural plants, which shows its superiority among so many other soaps.
- The latter have spoken of the inferiority of Mateja soap.
- It is not as widespread on the market as other soaps
- It doesn't achieve the expected effect after use
- There are other dermatological soaps that are more effective than Mateja soap.
- It has an unpleasant odor.
- Question 5: What do you think is mateja's competitive soap?
- Cintol
- Germol
- Dettol
- Sivoderm
- None

➤ *L'interprétation*

The results presented and analyzed in section 2 will be interpreted with the aim of making them more comprehensive by means of a review. This interpretation will focus on two key points:

- A critical look at the perception of Mateja soap's competitive advantage through advertising content
- The position in relation to the research hypothesis.

➤ *Criticisms of Mateja Soap's Perceived Competitive Edge Through Advertising Content.*

In fact, the survey conducted among residents of the Lemba commune shows that Mateja soap has achieved a high level of brand awareness. All those surveyed claimed to know Mateja soap. In this case, the soap's advertising campaign achieved its cognitive objective, revealing a high level of awareness of Mateja.

Spontaneous and aided awareness has been well taken into account by communication activities in favor of Mateja soap. Respondents recognize the product's name without any difficulty. Television is the communication medium that has helped Mateja soap become better known.

Marsavco invests heavily in television advertising to assert the identity of its Mateja product on the market. Television has made Mateja soap present in the eyes of Congolese viewers. This communication medium was used because of its proximity advantages. Television facilitates the visibility of Mateja soap in the eyes of the Congolese public, thanks to its qualities and semiological characteristics. Given that the population surveyed recognizes this soap so easily, we understand that the desired positioning that Marsavco builds on Mateja soap is actually perceived as such by its target audience.

Mateja's advertising communication faithfully and perfectly expresses the competitive advantages that Congolese consumers can derive from Mateja soap.

The product is understood as a dermatological soap that acts to improve the skin of infected people. As for Mateja's advertising message, it was found to be comprehensive after exposure. Mateja's advertising was well thought-out and designed to highlight the consumer advantages or benefits that could satisfy the need felt in the Congolese market in relation to skin hygiene. Another

category of consumers surveyed appreciated the value of Mateja's advertising, but felt that it took several exposures before they understood it.

This section of the population follows Mateja's advertising without much attention, due to a superficiality that makes understanding the message very slow. Mateja soap has succeeded in stimulating primary demand among Congolese consumers. Most of those interviewed consume this dermatological soap. This product is appreciated for its achievements in solving problems experienced by Congolese consumers.

Nevertheless, the frequency of purchase of this soap is lower, as the people questioned accept to consume Mateja soap a few times in relation to their frequency. In this respect, there is a problem with the purchase of the product, which is still in the launch phase of its life cycle.

However, the need content or Mateja's actions perform on users' bodies. These competitive advantages are judged comparatively superior to other similar product ranges. This demonstrates that the qualities touted by Mateja's advertising are indeed grasped and interpreted as such by the Congolese public. Unfortunately, some Congolese consumers find Mateja qualitatively inferior to other similar soaps which have also achieved the same notoriety score as Mateja, including flanelle, maxiderm, sivoderm, safiderm, Dettol and Germol.

III. CONCLUSION

The aim of our study was to understand how the public in Kinshasa, specifically the inhabitants of the Echangeur district, perceive the communicative elements of Mateja soap's competitive advantage.

Indeed, through the hopes and fears they inspire, advertising communication highlighting the product's qualities and characteristics acts on the conviction of consumers' will.

We have explored the field of advertising communication by studying its effectiveness in promoting a product. Our work aimed to demonstrate the role of competitive advantage in strengthening the effectiveness of advertising communication. We found that the majority of advertisements produced in Kinshasa feature the competitive advantage of the products sold.

However, many other advertising designers fail to promote competitive advantage in the expressive content of advertising messages broadcast in Kinshasa.

REFERENCES

- [1]. BARRE,S. et GAYRARD-CARRERA,A.-MARIE, La boîte à outils de la publicité, Paris, éd. DUNOD,2015,
- [2]. BELCH E &alii, La communication marketing, une perspective intégrée, Montréal, éd. ChanelièreInc, , 2005,
- [3]. CAUMONT D., La publicité, éd. Dunod, Paris,
- [4]. CHARAUDEAU P, Discours d'information médiatique : La construction du miroir social, Paris, éd. Nathan, , 1997,
- [5]. CHARROND, Une introduction à la communication, Montréal, éd. PUQ, , 1999,
- [6]. DECAUDIN J.M, La communication marketing, Paris , 3è éd. Economica, , 2004,
- [7]. DEMEURE C, Marketing : aide-mémoire, Paris, éd. Dalloz,2003,
- [8]. LAMBIN J-J, Le marketing stratégique, Paris, M.C Graw Hill, 1986,
- [9]. NKONSONLOMBI, Toh, Notes de cours de la communication globale (interne et externe),L2 CO, UPN,2019.